

B1202

Improved mesoporous scaffolds for composite electrodes in solid oxide devices for direct hydrogen production

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Abstract

The utilization of nanocomposite electrodes has been proven as an effective approach to enhance the performances of Solid Oxide Cell (SOC) devices. Among different strategies, the employment of mesoporous materials synthesized by hard-template methods came to the fore because of their elevated degree of porosity and the high level of provided percolation. Moreover, their use mitigates the formation of high current-density paths. Nano casting method allows the fabrication of high ordered microstructures presenting good thermal distribution through the electrode. Gadolinium-doped ceria (CGO - $Ce_{1-x}Gd_xO_{2-x/2}$) is one of the state-of-the-art materials on SOC devices [1] due to its remarkable ionic conductivity and its high thermochemical stability. CGO is employed as a porous backbone and is typically infiltrated by perovskite catalysts such $La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO_{3-\delta}$ (LSC), $La_{1-x}Sr_xMnO_3$ (LSM) or $La_{1-x}Sr_xCo_{1-y}Fe_yO_{3-\delta}$ (LSCF) [2] for the fabrication of SOC oxygen electrodes. The large utilization of mesoporous CGO backbones have been limited so far by: i) thermal stability during the processing steps of the device and ii) silica contamination coming from the template, which could inhibit the ionic conductivity of the material and affect the final performances [3].

A two-fold route was developed for overcoming such drawbacks by ex-situ chemical removal of the residual SiO_2 and by decoration with cobalt oxide (sintering aid) and presented in a dedicated study [4]. The CGO mesoporous powders were used as backbone for the oxygen electrode fabrication in a complete SOC, which was electrochemically tested in SOFC and SOEC configuration, showing high performances ($1.35 W cm^{-2}$ at 0.7 V and an injected current of $1.30 A cm^{-2}$ at 1.3 V, respectively, at $T = 750 ^\circ C$) overcomes state-of-the-art benchmark cells with similar configuration and sparks the interest towards novel strategies based on ceramic nanocomposites for SOC application [4].

In this contribution is reported the electrochemical characterization by impedance spectroscopy after a durability test made on this device for 1000 h at $750 ^\circ C$ applying a current density of $0.5 A cm^{-2}$. Such test showed a degradation rate of $\approx 125 mV kh^{-1}$.

Introduction

In the recent years the increasing demand for sustainable energy sources and for new and more efficient conversion strategies, focused the attention on solid oxide cells (SOCs) [5]. SOC can work as fuel cells to produce energy from hydrogen or other biofuels (e.g. Methane) or as electrolyser cells, to produce hydrogen from the separation of water or syngas through the co-electrolysis process of water and carbon dioxide [6,7]. In particular, the production of syngas is of great importance for the generation of chemicals or liquid fuels via Fischer-Tropsch synthesis [8]. SOC are characterized by high efficiencies, which grant high energy conversion percentage (70-80%), due to the relatively high operating temperature (600-900 °C) [9,10].

The typical materials used for manufacturing such devices are nickel oxide and yttria-stabilized zirconia (NiO-YSZ) for the fuel electrode, which is often the thicker layer and is generally the part of the cell that should also provide mechanical stability. The dense electrolyte is usually made of YSZ, which should guarantee a good ionic conductivity and the gas tightness of the system [2]. The oxygen electrode is generally composed by perovskite materials because they can provide an excellent electronic conductivity, as happens for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{MnO}_3$ (LSM), and even a mixed ionic-electronic conductivity (MIEC) as in the case of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_{3-\delta}$ (LSC), or $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{Co}_{1-y}\text{Fe}_y\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSCF) [2]. However, the ionic conductivity of these materials is not sufficient to guarantee high performances, therefore they are often coupled with other types of ceramics like gadolinium-doped ceria (CGO - $\text{Ce}_{1-x}\text{Gd}_x\text{O}_{2-x/2}$), which is known to be an excellent ionic conductor [11]. Together they can form highly efficient composite electrodes and increase the triple phase boundary (TPB), which is formed between ionic and electronic conductor species when they are contact with the gas [1,12].

Among different characteristics, the electrode should guarantee a certain degree of porosity (to allow the penetration of the gas to the active part), mechanical stability and, as already mentioned, both ionic and electronic conductivity [13].

A beneficial approach for maximizes the performances of such electrodes is the infiltration of nanostructured architectures, which can provide a good thermal distribution on the area of the electrode and a high surface area. In previous reports of our group were produced ceria-based mesoporous materials (pore size 2-50 nm) with measured BET areas $> 100 \text{ g cm}^{-2}$ [14]. Such mesoporous materials are synthesized via hard templating method by the utilization of a commercial silica template (KIT-6), which is usually removed through the washing by an alkaline solution [14]. Unfortunately, a considerable silica contamination remains localized at the grain boundaries of the mesoporous powders causing some limitation to the ionic conductivity of the material [3]. Moreover, such mesoporous materials cannot be fired at high temperature because their high reactivity. Such reactivity generates also a certain evolution of the nanostructure with the temperature, reaching the extreme case of the collapse of the backbone structure for temperature above 1000 °C [15].

For such reasons, a dedicated study was conducted, focused on the solution of these two specific issues [4]. The approach involved an additional cleaning step by hydrofluoric acid, known for its ability to easily dissolved silica, and to the utilization of Co oxide as sintering aid, to decrease the firing temperature of the mesoporous CGO [16,17]. The performances showed were high, with a peak power density $\approx 1.35 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ at 0.7 V in fuel cell configuration and an injected current of $\approx 1.30 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$ at 1.3 V in co electrolysis mode at $T = 750 \text{ °C}$ [4]. A durability test of overall 1000 h was conducted in co electrolysis showing a drop in performances around 125 mV kh^{-1} [4]. In this contribution is reported the electrochemical characterization made on the cell by impedance spectroscopy before and after the durability test. Such results, together with a microstructural characterization of the cell after operation, are here discussed to explain the reasons of the degradation.

1. Scientific Approach

Mesoporous $\text{Ce}_{0.8}\text{Gd}_{0.2}\text{O}_{1.9}$ was synthesized by hard template method using a commercial silica template named KIT-6. Nitrate precursor in stoichiometric proportion ($\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Gd}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were dissolved in ethanol together with the KIT-6, dried and then calcinated at 600 °C for 5 h. Subsequently, the silica was removed by washing firstly with a solution 2M of NaOH and secondly with water. A detailed description of the method could be found elsewhere [18].

The mesoporous powder was etched also with hydrofluoric acid (2.5 %v/v) to remove the residual SiO_2 contamination coming from the template and decorated with Co Oxide (1 %mol) as sintering aids, to lower the firing temperature of the scaffold. The procedure is exposed in detail in a dedicated work of the group [4].

A complete SOC with a thick fuel electrode (300 μm) of NiO-YSZ and a dense electrolyte of YSZ (7 μm) both made by tape casting (SOLIDpower, SPA). On top of the half-cell was deposited a CGO barrier layer by PLD to separate the YSZ from the Sr-rich species present in the oxygen electrode ($\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$, sintered at 1200 °C) and a rugosity layer of commercial CGO powder by airbrush (sintered at 1250 °C). Subsequently the CGO mesoporous scaffold was airbrushed on top of the rugosity layer (thickness $\approx 10\text{-}15 \mu\text{m}$) and sintered at 850 °C. The backbone was infiltrated by LSCF precursor solution and calcinated afterward at 800 °C. Eventually a final layer of commercial LSCF was airbrushed ($\approx 20\text{-}25 \mu\text{m}$) on top of the CGO scaffold and sintered at 850 °C [4].

A Durability of 1000 h was conducted in COSOEC configuration (65% H_2O , 25% CO_2 and 10% H_2 , gas composition at the fuel electrode) applying 0.5 A cm^{-2} at 750 °C, highlighting a voltage increase of 125 mV kh^{-1} [4].

In this contribution firstly, a microstructural characterization of the mesoporous powders synthesized for fabricating the function layer is reported. Secondly, the electrochemical characterization of the cell by impedance spectroscopy, before and after the durability test is presented and discussed. Eventually SEM cross section micrographs of different part of the cell are presented to rationalize the results obtained from the fitting of the impedance spectra.

2. Experiments

The microstructural analysis was conducted using a Carl ZEISS Auriga scanning electron microscope (SEM) with an energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) detector, by X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements (2θ range 20° to 90°) on a Bruker-D8 Advance instrument at room temperature using Cu-K α radiation and by Expert-Pro Diffractometer (Cu-K α 1 and Cu-K α 2 radiation) in the 2θ range 0.2° and 5°. The SOC was tested inside a ProboStat™ (NorECS AS) station, using a tubular furnace to reach the operating temperature (750 °C) and Ceramabond™ (Aremco) as sealant, to ensure the gas separation between the two electrodes. An M9700 electronic load from Maynuo Electronic Co was used to test the electrochemical properties of the cell, under co-electrolysis (gas composition 65% H_2O , 25% CO_2 and 10% H_2), while a Novocontrol spectrometer from NOVOCONTROL Technologies GmbH & Co. KG was utilized for the EIS characterization.

3. Results

Fig. 1 shows two SEM images at different magnification (Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b) where is presented the repetitive structure of the mesoporous. One can notice the presence of some elongated particles together with the synthesized CGO powders, which are probably due to the incomplete removal of the silica.

Fig. 1: a) Micrograph of the mesoporous CGO after the cleaning by NaOH. b) High magnification picture of the same zone.

Fig. 2 shows the results of the characterization on the mesoporous powders etched by HF and decorated by Co oxide. The synthesized powders analyzed by XRD (Fig 2a) show the typical peaks of the CGO, while after the etching by HF some new peaks appear on the pattern. Such peaks have been recognized as Gd and Ce-rich fluorite phases due to a partial etching of the hydrofluoric acid to the mesoporous powders [4]. However, the small angle XRD analysis of Fig. 2b demonstrates that the repetitive structure of the mesoporous CGO it is not affected by the etching. In the aforementioned work of the group focused on the optimization of such structures, the amount of SiO₂ after and before the etching is measured by Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), with the silica content which passes from 0.9 %wt. to 0.2 %wt. respectively [4].

Fig. 2: a) XRD on the mesoporous powders before and after the etching by HF and b) small angle XRD of the two powders compared with the pattern from the KIT-6 template.

The cell produced with the nanostructured functional layer, was tested on co-electrolysis mode for 1000 h with an applied current 0.5 A cm⁻², showing an increment of voltage of 125 mV kh⁻¹ [4]. EIS spectroscopy measurement at the OCV were conducted after (Fig. 3a) and before (Fig. 3b) the durability test. An equivalent circuit (inset figures 3a and 3b), made by an inductance (L), a serial resistance (R_s) and two ZARC elements (R_{p1}Q₁ and R_{p2}Q₂) was utilized for the fitting of the impedance spectra.

Fig. 3: EIS measurements were conducted at OCV b) at the starting point and c) after 1000 h of durability test. The fitting was made using an equivalent circuit with 2 ZARC elements.

The results of the fitting, which are reported on table 1, highlight two different contribution one at ≈ 1000 Hz ($R_{p1}Q_1$) and a second one at ≈ 1 Hz ($R_{p2}Q_2$). The first element presents a capacitance value which passes from $5.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ F cm² to $5.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ F cm². The characteristic frequencies and the capacitance values are typical for charge transfer phenomena happening at the composite electrodes [19,20]. On the other hand, the second ZARC element presents a capacitance which remains in both cases around 10^{-1} F cm⁻² and considering the characteristic frequency (≈ 1 Hz) could be assign to gas diffusion phenomena or gas conversion, processes usually dominated by the fuel electrode which is the thicker layer [19–21].

Table 1: Results of the fitting on the impedance measurements of Fig. 3a and 3b.

	t = 0	t = 1000 h
L (H)	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-7}$
R_s (Ω cm²)	$6.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$
R_{p1} (Ω cm²)	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$
C_{p1} (F cm⁻²)	$5.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
f₁ (Hz)	$8.9 \cdot 10^2$	$2.6 \cdot 10^3$
R_{p2} (Ω cm²)	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-1}$
C_{p2} (F cm⁻²)	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-1}$
f₂ (Hz)	1.9	4.9
ASR_{pol} (Ω cm²)	0.19	0.32
ASR_{tot} (Ω cm²)	0.26	0.40

The results reported on table 1 clarify that the high frequency element is the one which shows the more consistent evolution during the degradation, with a resistance which passes from $3.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ Ω cm² to $1.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$ Ω cm². This could be explained by both an evolution of the mesoporous structure after many hours of operation, due to an increase of the reactivity of the CGO due to the removal of the SiO₂ particles or by a degradation at the fuel electrode level, which could be caused by a progressive deactivation of the metallic Ni present in the cermet. These deactivation phenomena are extensively studied in literature and are mainly caused by coarsening of the metallic Ni particles or by its evaporation from the electrode [22,23].

Fig. 4 shows the cell microstructure after the degradation. On Fig. 4a the oxygen electrode is presented, while Fig. 4b shows the electrolyte with the CGO barrier layer.

Fig. 4c shows a micrograph obtained using a SEM in-lens detector and acquired at low voltage acceleration (≈ 1 kV) in which the bright zones represent the percolating metallic Ni, while the dark ones are the ensemble of YSZ and all the non-percolating Ni particles [24,25]. Fig. 4d presents a high magnification image of the barrier layer where some nanosized voids can be observed [26].

Probably the nanosized voids formation on the barrier layer do not have a strong impact on the performance of the cell. Their presence should be affecting mostly the ohmic contribution, which passes from $6.8 \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ to $8.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ from the starting point to the end of the durability test.

The significant growth of the high frequency arc should be correlated by a microstructural evolution of the electrodes. Even if an evolution of the oxygen electrode could not be excluded, the fuel electrode presents poor electronic percolation near the electrolyte after the durability test (Fig.c). Therefore, the main cause of degradation could be attributed to a certain deactivation of the cermet close to the interface with the dense YSZ layer.

Fig. 4: the figure shows a) the oxygen electrode made of mesoporous CGO infiltrated by LSCF solution, b) the electrolyte and barrier layer of the measured cell. An in-les picture c) taken at low acceleration voltage of the fuel electrode and d) a high magnification picture of defects of the barrier layer.

Conclusion

A solid oxide cell device with a nanostructured CGO oxygen electrode infiltrated by LSCF was tested in co-electrolysis (65% H₂O, 25% CO₂ and 10% H₂) for 1000 h applying a current of 0.5 A cm². The cell presented a degradation around 125 mV kh⁻¹ and impedance spectroscopy measurements were made after and before the durability test.

Two different arcs were individuated by EIS characterization at 1000 Hz and at 1 Hz attributed to charge transfer processes which could happen at both electrodes and to gas diffusion or conversion at the fuel electrode, respectively. The former seems to be the responsible of the degradation of the cells, passing from $3.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ to $1.1 \cdot 10^{-1} \Omega \text{ cm}^2$.

The microstructural characterization highlights the presence of nanosized voids at the barrier layer, which should not be related with the evolution of the high frequency arc, and of a certain lack of electronic percolation in the vicinity of the interface fuel electrode/electrolyte. Such depletion of percolating metalling Ni is strongly affecting the degradation process.

Acknowledgements

The authors want to acknowledge the financial support of the “Generalitat de Catalunya” (2017 SGR 1421, NANOEN) and the IREC fellowship grant. Part of the research has received funding from the ECo project (ref. 699892) and the 3D-MADE project (ENE2016-74889-C4- 1-R).

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Keywords: EFCF2020, SOx

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